

CORRELATION OF CLINICAL FINDINGS OF PERINATAL HYPOXIA WITH CRANIAL SONOGRAPHIC FINDINGS IN TERM BABIES

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Abstract

Despite of many advances in knowledge and technologies perinatal hypoxia is still a lethal condition leading to morbidity and mortality. Most of the studies reported in literature, described parenchymal abnormalities in neonate's brain and its finding have good correlation with MRI. This particular study was however planned to find out the correlation among clinical findings and cranial sonographic findings in term babies within three days presented with perinatal hypoxia. Ultrasound is used as screening tool for hypoxic neonates with hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) because within three days MRI was not recommended.

Objective: The objective of the study was to assess the correlation among clinical findings of perinatal hypoxia and cranial sonographic findings in term babies.

Methodology: A correlational study was carried out on one hundred and thirty eight neonates in Neonatal Unit of Children's Hospital Lahore. Data was selected on the basis of laid down criteria through questionnaire and analyzed by SPSS version 16.0.

Result: Out of 138 neonates, 99 were males and 39 were females with birth weight (1.2-4.0 kg) having mean \pm SD 2.73 ± 0.42 . HIE grades (mild, moderate and severe) were found in 14, 117, 7 babies respectively and ultrasound grades 0 (normal/ mild echogenic), grade 1 (moderate echogenic) and grade 2 (severe/generalized echogenic) were found in 47, 71, 20 neonates respectively with $r= 0.427$ and $P\text{-value } 0.000 < 0.05$ showing significant moderate positive correlation.

Conclusion: Cranial ultrasound is a good screening tool to evaluate hypoxic changes in neonatal brain. It has a significant correlation with clinical findings.

INTRODUCTION

Delayed cry after birth or failure to initiate breathing as long as 1 minute after birth is a criterion of perinatal hypoxia according to WHO. It happens at

birth so it is also known as birth hypoxia¹. It occurs due to oxygen deficiency to brain leading to ischemia. Due to this, vital organs like kidneys,

lungs, liver are badly affected but severe and serious damage may occur to brain.^{2, 3, 4} Perinatal hypoxia is a serious medical problem contributing to neonatal mortality and morbidity in whole world.² Incidence of perinatal hypoxia in developed countries is 1-1.5% and in Pakistan is 3.3%.⁵ According to WHO, each year 4 million newborns develop hypoxia in which 1.2 million die and same percentage may develop severe neurological consequences like hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy, epilepsy, cerebral palsy, developmental delay out of 130 million each year globally.³

Common symptoms of hypoxia before birth are abnormal fetal heart rate and low pH levels and at the time of birth, it leads to fetal cyanosis, low heart rate, weak muscle tone, weak breathing, meconium stained amniotic fluid, APGAR score of 0 to 3 for longer than 5 minutes, CNS problems including coma, seizure, and problems with other systems, like circulatory, digestive, and respiratory systems.⁶ Perinatal hypoxia is divided into antepartum, intrapartum and fetal.⁷

Failure to initiate breathing at birth leads to hypoxic ischemic injury to the brain resulting a clinical disease termed as hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy. It damages brain leading to developmental delay, cerebral palsy, mental retardation or neonatal death.⁸ Imaging is also done in case of perinatal hypoxia for the assessment of neurological condition of a newborn that includes cranial ultrasonography, cranial CT, cranial MRI. Cranial ultrasonography is comparatively a simple tool. In addition to free of radiation, it is also non-invasive, fast and cost effective technique.^{9, 10} Due to its portable quality, it can be performed easily at bedside in NICU unit. It is a safer technique and easily approachable by a common person.

According to a previous study, echogenicity changes in brain WM (white matter) was scored according to the classification by van Wezel-meijler et al. In this Grade 0 show normal echogenicity of the periventricular WM. Grade 1 show moderately increased periventricular WM echogenicity, showing the affected region being bright or as bright as the choroid plexus. And Grade 2 show severely increased generalized echogenicity, in which the affected region being brighter than the choroid plexus.¹¹

In a previous study perinatal asphyxia in term babies by Roberto Antonucci, Annalisa Porcella and Maria Dolores Pilloni (2014),² asphyxia is considered as a severe condition that leads to mortality and morbidity. Both antepartum and intrapartum risk factors are associated with perinatal asphyxia which may affect any organ but hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy is mostly studied clinical condition and is burdened with the most severe sequelae. After HIE, feasibility of providing neuroprotection by hypothermia therapy is helpful to reduce the risk of death or major neurodevelopmental disability. According to author, many promising neuroprotective agents might contribute to reduce hypoxic-ischemic brain injury through different mechanisms of action, but further studies are required to confirm their efficacy. The prognosis is dependent on the severity of the perinatal asphyxia. Only a minority of infants with severe HIE survive without being handicapped.²

In a previous study, diagnosis of hypoxic ischemic cerebral lesions of the newborn by ultrasound, Ioana Alina Ancain (2011)¹¹ said that most widely used neuroimaging technique in newborn babies is transcranial ultrasound. By this technique, we can assess the neurologic condition in babies by diagnosing different grades / stages and information's about immediate and long term prognosis can be achieved. In this study features of ultrasound are noted in two pathological conditions, peri and intraventricular hemorrhages and periventricular leukomalacia, which cause severe brain damage secondary to perinatal hypoxia.¹¹

According to a study by Imran Ahmed (2010)⁹ role of cranial sonography and CT scanning in neonatal intracranial ischemia and hemorrhage by ultrasound is considered as a better modality for imaging in preterm neonates with suspected intraventricular hemorrhage or periventricular leucomalacia and unreliable in the imaging of term newborns with suspected HII. While CT or MRI is considered a better modality for suspected HII.⁹

Another study by Olusanya BO and Solanke OA (2010),¹³ correlates of birth asphyxia using two Apgar score classification methods by explain that birth asphyxia in both preterm and term babies is affected by the five-minute Apgar score classification method.¹³

In study of Talal Waqar and Khalid Haque (2012),¹⁴birth asphyxia is considered a leading cause of neonatal mortality and morbidity in Pakistan. Large proportions of survivors go on to develop cerebral palsy contributing to the largest group of intellectually and physically challenged individuals in our society. This study provides pragmatic but evidence based guidelines on the management of neonates suffering from birth asphyxia in Pakistan.¹⁴ The rationale of this study is to correlate the clinical findings (hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy grades) of perinatal hypoxia with cranial sonographic findings (ultrasound grades) in full term babies within three days of birth.

Methodology

Our study was a correlational analytical study. The study setting was Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) of Children's Hospital Lahore. The study was conducted for duration of 9 months with a sample size of 138 individuals after approval from Institutional Review Board of University of Lahore. The sampling technique used was convenient non-probability sampling. In sample selection criteria the inclusion criteria was full term newborns of gestational age >37 weeks having clinical history of perinatal hypoxia or history of delayed cry at the time of birth. Preterm babies and babies more than three days were excluded. The data was collected through proper questionnaire. Proper consent was taken from the patient's parents or guardian.

Sample of population was studied by Toshiba Famiio 8 (Ultrasound machine) with curvilinear probe having frequency 3-6 MHz. The subject was placed in supine position during scan. Standard images in sagittal and coronal planes were obtained through the anterior fontanelle.

The collected data was stored as excel sheets and EXCEL and SPSS software's was used to apply relevant test for the statistical analysis. The quantitative data (birth weight, age) presented in form of mean \pm S.D and for qualitative data (gender, HIE grades (mild, moderate, severe), ultrasound grades (mild, moderate, severe) percentage and frequency were calculated and bar charts or pie charts were drawn. Spearman rho correlation was applied.

RESULTS

Total 138 neonates were included in this study in which 99 were male and 39 were female. 26 babies were in their first day of life. 49 were of two days and 63 of three days. Maximum and minimum birth weight of 138 babies was 4.0 and 1.2 respectively. The mean \pm S.D of birth weight were 2.73 ± 0.42 kg. All of 138 babies had history of delayed cry. Grades of hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy were assigned to neonates according to their condition. 14 were of grade 1 (mild). 117 and 7 were of grade 2 (moderate) and grade 3 (severe) respectively. (Table 1). 10.1% showed grade I, 84.8% showed grade II and 5.1% showed grade III (Graph 1)

Table 1: Hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) Grades

HIE Grade				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Grade I	14	10.1	10.1	10.1
Grade II	117	84.8	84.8	94.9
Grade III	7	5.1	5.1	100.0
Total	138	100.0	100.0	

Graph 1: Grades of hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (HIE)

Ultrasound grades were suggested according to their findings during scan. Out of 138 babies, 47, 71 and 20 subjects were given grade 0 (mild), 1 (moderate) and 2 (severe) respectively. (Table 2)

34.1% showed grade 0, 51.4% showed grade 2 and 14.5% showed grade 3 (Graph 2)

Table 2: Ultrasound grades

Ultrasound Grades

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Grade 0	47	34.1	34.1	34.1
Grade 1	71	51.4	51.4	85.5
Grade 2	20	14.5	14.5	100.0
Total	138	100.0	100.0	

Graph 2: Ultrasound Grades

Spearman rho correlation was applied. A moderate positive correlation was observed between hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) grades and ultrasound grades with $r = 0.427$ with P-value $0.000 < 0.05$ which is statistically significant. (Table 3)

Table 3: Correlation between HIE and Ultrasound Grades

Correlations				
			G	U
Spearman's rho	HIE Grade	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.427**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	138	138
	Ultrasound Grade	Correlation Coefficient	.427**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	138	138

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Discussion

Perinatal hypoxia is defined as delayed cry after birth or respiratory failure due to lack of oxygen and is a leading cause of mortality and morbidity in Pakistan.¹ It develop severe neurological consequences in which hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) is mostly studied and a complicated condition.^{1, 2, 3} Perinatal hypoxia is also known as hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) as described in previous researches. Stages/grades of HIE were given according to Sarnat staging in my research and in all others previous researches.⁸ Imaging study are usually done in all neonates. Cranial ultrasound is an initial and immediately available imaging modality and also a reliable technique for evaluation of neonatal brain to

demonstrate cerebral injuries. It is a safe and routine tool in neonatology department for newborn babies who suffered in different problems like perinatal hypoxia to review normal anatomy, ventricle size, focal or diffuse increased echogenicity in cerebral hemispheres and cortex and basal ganglia lesions.¹⁰ Other modalities are CT and MRI. MRI is considered as a gold standard tool to evaluate cerebral injuries. But it is expensive, require sedation, take more time and in very ill patients it cannot be easily perform as compared to the ultrasound.^{9, 10, 15} In previous study Pilvilves said that although having some limitations, ultrasound illustrated parenchymal abnormalities in neonate's brain and its finding also have good correlation with MRI.¹⁵ In my research only ultrasound is used as

screening tool for hypoxic neonates with HIE because within three days MRI was not recommended by doctor. It is also an expensive procedure, so everybody cannot afford it easily. In previous articles, APGAR scoring classification is considered as a predictor of perinatal hypoxia in both preterm and term babies.¹³ In this study APGAR score is not mentioned because babies admitted in hospital were referred from others places. APGAR score was not mentioned in their medical records file and their relatives were unaware about APGAR score. Therefore, only history of delayed cry is taken by them. In previous research van Wezel-meijler et al performed a study in preterm babies and presence of echogenicity changes in brain WM was scored according to his own classification known as van Wezel-meijler et al classification on cranial ultrasound and then compared with MRI.¹¹ In current study clinical findings including full term babies, birth weight, history of delayed cry and most important HIE grades were taken according to the condition of the patients and ultrasound was done within first 3 days of life in full term babies and grades were given according to findings. My grading on ultrasound was done according to van Wezel-meijler et al classification. In this grading grade 0 showed normal parenchymal echogenicity, grade 1 showed moderately increased echogenicity and grade 2 showed severely increased parenchymal echogenicity. HIE grades were given by doctors according to Sarnat stages/grades. In my study 99 were male and 39 were female neonates out of 138. In these 26 babies were in their first day of life. 49 babies of second day of life and 63 were in their third day of life. Mean birth weight was 1.2-4.0 (minimum to maximum) having mean 2.73 and standard deviation 0.42. According to HIE grading 14 babies were mild (grade I), 117 were moderate (grade II) and 7 were severe (grade III). On ultrasound 47 babies showed normal or mild increased parenchymal echogenicity (grade 0), 71 showed moderate (grade 1) and 20 showed severe or generalized increased parenchymal echogenicity (grade 2). After collecting all data correlation was found out by using SPSS software. I found that there is a significant moderate positive correlation between clinical findings (HIE grades I, II, III) and sonographic findings (Ultrasound grades 0, 1, 2)

with $r = + 0.427$ and P-value $0.000 < 0.05$ which is statistically significant.

Conclusion

Ultrasound is a good screening tool to evaluate parenchymal echogenicity of brain in newborn babies during early 3 days of life. Due to non-invasive modality it is a safe technique for newborns. There is a moderate positive correlation of ultrasound with clinical findings in babies suffering in perinatal hypoxia.

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